

Diversifying revenue in rural Africa through circular, sustainable and replicable biobased solutions and business models

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the training part and first results of the accelerator program of BIO4AFRICA H2020 project (Contract no. 101000762) corresponding to D6.4 Achievements and impact of the BIO4AFRICA Accelerator (M36,) led by BPE.

This report presents the cohort of the 20 companies selected in the accelerator program, 5 companies per country (Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Senegal and Uganda). The 20 selected companies show all the value chain, from small and individual farmers selling products with low value in a very local market to farmers being part of a big cooperative selling value-added products in the international market.

This report describes the execution of the training program, that includes 4 bootcamps, one per country, mentoring program focus on circular economy through the technologies developed in BIO4Africa and customized interviews, one per company, during the visits one to one on the field.

This report presents, as well, the first results after the training part thanks to the design of a road map, one per company, describing a list of actions to execute during the 2024 to improve every company under the triple perspective: management, circular economy and social impact.

The objective of the training part identifies key aspects, optimal scenarios and different business models to scale up and deploy the bio-based technological solutions in Africa in the agrobusiness sector.

It is during the Management Support program, from January to December 2024, when the focus will go to the execution, trying to impact as much as possible to the 20 companies selected.

The conclusions present first actions and results providing from the execution plan under the Management Support Program customized per every company.

2. RATIONALE

Africa will need to feed 1.2 billion people by 2030 and over 2 billion by 2050 and, almost 20% of Africa's population is affected by undernourishment. Additionally, 60% of sub-Saharan African land is used for grazing animals, and many people combine crop farming with livestock production, which is crucial for livelihoods across the continent. Livestock is a valuable asset for rural communities, pulling power for ploughs and transport, creating income diversification via nutrient-rich animal products, as well as being key to reclaiming degraded land and conserving soil integrity and water.

BIO4Africa will contribute to Africa's food and nutritional security by combatting poverty, while driving inclusive and sustainable rural development. Furthermore, BIO4Africa will support the deployment of the bioeconomy in rural Africa via the development of bio-based solutions and value chains with a circular approach to drive the cascading use of local resources and diversify the income of farmers.

The ultimate focus is on transferring simple, small-scale, and robust bio-based techs adapted to local biomass, needs and contexts, including green biorefinery, pyrolysis, hydrothermal carbonisation, briquetting, pelletising, bio-composites, and bioplastics production.

In doing so BIO4Africa aims to empower farmers to sustainably produce a variety of higher value bio-based products and energy, including: animal feed, biochar, bio composites, bioplastics that can be used as fertilisers, pollutant absorbents, construction materials, packaging, solid fuel for cooking, and ingredients for biogas production. These uses significantly improve the environmental, economic and social performance of their forage agri-food systems. BIO4Africa has set up four pilot cases with different testing sites in Uganda, Ghana, Senegal and Côte d'Ivoire, offering more than 300 farmers and farmer groups, including small dairies and lower-income farmers, women farmer groups and transhumant pastoralists, the opportunity to test them in real productive conditions.

Under this overall context, BIO4Africa aims to provide rural communities with diverse options for taking up the bio-based solutions into their agri-food systems using bio-based business models that are sustainable. It will do so, by employing analytical and design tools well-fit for sustainability-oriented business models and deploying participatory activities to co-design, test and validate these models alongside rural community stakeholders (farmers, bio-based experts, extension services, development partners, local authorities, policy makers, etc.).

3. SCOPE OF THE BIO4AFRICA TASK 6.2

The activities of this task aim at designing and deploying an acceleration programme to foster bio-based business amongst farmers and rural communities in Africa, enabling them to explore and seize bio-based business opportunities, leveraging the technologies developed by BIO4AFRICA.

The programme will include a series of business development support services to candidates interested in replicating and / or scaling our business models:

(i) Business training: Local bootcamps (1 per country) will engage candidates into rigorous bio-based business training on key entrepreneurship aspects (strategy definition, business model identification, financial planning, marketing, business planning and benchmarking and disruptive vision development) delivered by BPE as well as on digital transformation and agricultural production aspects delivered by AATF;

(ii) Mentoring: Selected experts from BPE and AATF will coach and offer tailored CEO management support to selected candidates with a focus on building their capacity for decision making and management, both of which are crucial contributing factors for safeguarding the survivability and ultimately the success of a company.

(iii) Access to finance support: BPE and AATF will mobilise their international network and facilitate access to finance support, loans and investments, supporting companies to find suitable modes of finance in Africa and EU.

4. THE ROADMAP

What's a road map? A list of actions – activity, cost and timing - to achieve a strategy starting from an initial business diagnosis. In Bio4Africa accelerator program we have evaluate three perspectives – management, circular economy and social impact.

We would like to present the results about the Bio4Africa portfolio business diagnosis.

4.1 Management perspective

We have identified four areas to evaluate the competitiveness of each business:

1. Fit to market
2. Productivity
3. Financials
4. Management and digital tools

Situation about **Fit to market**

- a. Add value. Only 6 over 20 has a product with add value. We have identified processed products like dry mango, mango vinegar, sunflower oil or certified products like cacao trade fair or cashew nuts Bio.
- b. Market fit. 2 companies are selling in the international market, 6 in national market and 12 in local market.
- c. Brand & image. 4 over 20 works on this trying to have a good market position.
- d. Packaging or bulk. 14 over 20 sells their products without packaging. We have identified packaging for international markets where quality, size and characteristics are defined by the clients, and national markets where all companies have a similar packaging without singularity versus the concurrence.
- e. Sales - logistics / transport. We would like to define two kinds of transport. Internal between small farmers units and cooperative collect hubs and external between cooperatives and market. We have 5 cooperatives that provides internal transport to their farmers. External transport is well resolved in 9 cooperatives.

Conclusions, objectives and actions

In general terms there is no uniqueness in the value proposition and distribution channels. That means low prices and not enough revenues.

Concerning the 20 examples coming from the accelerator program:

Worst position is for not processed products without volume and certification. They can be sold only in local markets without margin. Difficulty to move the production from the land to the market. Part of the production is sold at low prices.

Processed products in local or national market are packaged in similar size and design and they are offered in similar channels of distribution. Visiting different local points of distribution (small shops, markets, informal sellers etc.) we realized this general uniformity. The result is low prices and low margins. There is also a big issue with transport.

Better prices are linked to processed products ready to export. They have always a standard of quality – Bio or faire trade certification, international packaging requirements and volume.

Obviously objective must be focus on price and sales. The problem is when there is no possibility to add value or increase volume. Small farmers alone or cooperatives offering not processed products has big difficulties to increases revenues because they have capacity only to cover local markets.

Without trucks and small vehicles to collect and distribute all the crops, or adding some value transforming products there is no possibility to change the reality. Improvements can come only through investments, but this is another big issue to resolve we analyse after.

Situation about **productivity**

- f. Human resources. In general terms is not an issue in terms of number of people need to work in not qualified positions. It's an issue in some positions more qualified.
- g. Quality. Is the most important issue to resolve with processed and certified products and no questionable characteristic for export.
- h. Capacity. Without volume is not possible to achieve international or national markets. The destiny of the production is local. In our cohort we have 2 in international markets, 6 in national markets and 12 in local market.

Conclusions, objectives and actions

Without volume is not possible to sell in national markets and to achieve international markets is necessary to have volume and quality. Objectives are strategies to provide quality and increase productivity.

Situation about **financials**

- i. Financial needs to growth. 20 over 20, all the business has to invest. It doesn't matter about their initial position in terms of activity or market. From local small farmer selling in their area to a big cooperative selling abroad this is a problem to resolve. The difference come from their viability – capacity to generate profits and access to credit. 14 over 20 has very difficulties to cover the financial needs to growth.
- j. Margins. Not more than 8 business over 20 has acceptable margins. This is the starting point of the operational difficulties in cash flow and treasury. Margins without volume explain the difficulties to invest. In our cohort only 4 business have margins and volume.

Conclusions, objectives and actions

As we described previously margins and treasury are the main issues to resolve in agrobusiness sector in rural areas. Access to credit is also a big problem in Africa, banks doesn't offer competitive prices and works with low risks.

In Bio4africa cohort we have few examples of success and all of them are linked with big figures and international markets. The reality is international clients provide access to money through direct investments, commercial loans or advance payments.

Situation about **Management and tools**

- k. Professional manager – board. 4 over 20 have board and professional managers.
- l. Business Plan – strategy. 4 over 20 have a clear strategy and a Business Plan before the accelerator program.
- m. Budget and P&L. 4 over 20 have a budget and a P&L before the accelerator program.
- n. Data. 4 over 20 manage the business with data.

Conclusions, objectives and actions

In general terms agrobusiness sector is not professional in terms of management. They work without real figures doing more or less the same as always and without planification, all the activity is focus on short time. Objectives has to be focus on introduce management habits and tools.

4.2 Circular economy perspective

This perspective is very relevant into Bio4Africa project.

After the training program we realized we could implement real examples of biobased technologies in the accelerator program to complement the pilots.

When we designed the training program, we decided to focus the mentoring program on this perspective. We thought it was better to concentrate the support of the mentors on this and avoid to open other discussions related with other perspectives. We must say it was a very efficient decision.

Thanks to the mentoring program we have defined the initial situation concerning biobased technologies and the potentiality to be include during the Bio4Africa program in the following months.

Potentiality has to include two indicators (1) technology capacity – knowledge and access to technology (2) economic viability – investment versus profit or/and investment versus relevant cost decrease.

We would like to present the initial situation of biobased technologies, objectives, needs and actions to run during the program.

Table 1: Circular economy analysis Côte d'Ivoire

Company	Actual situation	Objectives	Needs	Actions
Ecookim	Biocompost, an easy way to reduce the pods in the farms but not enough. Cacao bio needs to ensure the traceability	1. Fish farm 2. Charbon from the pods (cabosses)	1. Know how nutrients 2. Technology briquettes	1. Contact with Ghana Bio4africa partners for fish nutrients 2. Student from INP-HB transformation pods to charbon and tech from Uganda
Kapatchiva	Biocompost, an easy way to reduce the pods in the farms but not enough. Cacao bio needs to ensure the traceability	1. Production the biochar	1. Financial needs (build a biochar plant)	1. Support from INP-HB University (students) to define the technological needs 2. Support from BPE to find financement for the infrastructure
Procanso	No actions to reduce the waste in the field.	No specific objective	No defined	1. Agree the objectives and road map with Procanso
Socaze	Biocompost, an easy way to reduce the pods in the farms but not enough. Cacao bio needs to ensure the traceability	1. Biochar	1. Know how from INP-HB	1. Define the circular economy model (they self or with INP-HB)
Agrim (*)	Rice waste from the transformation (without peel)	No specific objective	No defined	1. Small production. Not enough waste to transform in terms of additional income

Table 2: Circular economy analysis Senegal

Company	Actual situation	Objectives	Needs	Actions
Agropastoral	The peels and the rest of waste has not economic return. They give it without price	1. Evaluate the possibility to install one dryer hybrid (biogaz and solar) 2. Analyze how to concentrate all the waste and calculate the value	1. Know how and support from USAZ	1. Analyze with USAZ students the viability of the project
Demiir	The peels and the rest of waste has not economic return. They give it without price	1. Evaluate the possibility to install one dryer (biogaz) 2. Analyze how to concentrate all the waste and calculate the value	1. Know how and support from USAZ	1. Analyze with USAZ students the viability of the project
Waare	The peels and the rest of waste has not economic return. They give it without price	No need for support from Bio4africa in terms of circular economy	No need for support from Bio4Africa	No need for support from Bio4Africa
Ethicajou	They have broken pieces (good in terms of quality but not in size and aspect). They sell the shells at 7 Fcfa/kg	1. Evaluate the possibility to install one dryer (biogaz) 2. Analyze how to concentrate all the waste and calculate the value	1. Know how and support from USAZ	1. Analyze with USAZ students the viability of the project
Balantacounda	They don't have any return in economic terms from the waste. Shells, broken pieces etc.	1. Evaluate the possibility transform the shells in charbon	1. Know how and support from Bio4africa project Biostar	1. Analyze with USAZ students the viability of the project

Table 3: Circular economy analysis Uganda

Company	Actual situation	Objectives	Needs	Actions
Agali	So far, the cooperative does not do any processing with the waste, they just sell it for further processing	1. Better quality on animal feeds 2. Cooking fuel & electricity to the livelihood of the cooperative	1. Financial investment (Loan from the bank) 2. Know how from Bio4africa project	1. Define a project to develop
HOCW	They have a problem with plastic waste. They don't know how to manage 1200 households	1. Collect and sort plastic waste	1. Investment of 1.2 M Ugx to collect and sort plastic waste	1. Define a project to develop
PKWI	They have collection centers in which, the waste is collected	1. Briquettes for households	1. Investment for Briquettes machinery	1. Define a project to develop
HARUGONGO	So far, the cooperative does not do any processing with the waste	No specific objective	No defined	1. Very small productions spread throughout the territory

Table 4: Circular economy analysis Ghana

Company	Actual situation	Objectives	Needs	Actions
KOBU-BAMSIM Farmer group	Cowpea, soybean husk, corn cobs and rice husk are used to produce biochar. Plant residue is sold to Savanet at Ghc 20 per bag.	Provide SavaNet raw materials for Biochar production	Extension service from the SavaNet Agriculture Technology Research Station in Loagri-Ghana	collaborate with SavaNet and the Bio4Africa consortium members
Tiza Boora Farmer Cooperative	Corn cobs, groundnut husk, and rice husk is used to produce biochar for use by the farmers under the cooperative.	Produce Biochar for use by cooperative members for crop production on commercial scale.	Extension service from the SavaNet Agriculture Technology Research Station in Loagri-Ghana	collaborate with SavaNet and the Bio4Africa consortium members
Nasigiri farms	Rice bran, and crop residue is used to feed pigs on the farm. They are purchased from farmers at 10 Ghana cedis per1Kg.	Produce pigs using bio-based and conventional pig feed on commercial scale.	Investment to increase pig production using bio-based pig feed and technology.	collaborate with iHub and the Bio4Africa project consortium members
Romilla fish farms	Fish meal, soyabeans, corn etc are used to produce fish feed pellets on his farm. No waste generated.	Produce fish feed pellets and fish (Tilapia) on commercial scale using both bio-based and conventional feed.	Investment for the production of bio-based fish feed pellets on commercial scale.	collaborate with iHub and the Bio4Africa project consortium members

Conclusions, objectives and actions

Biobased technologies from farmer perspective have sense when there is enough volume to transform, and investment versus revenues or reduction costs are positive, is profitable, and managed by the cooperative. When biobased technologies are out of the cooperative and farmers have to grow some feedstocks to be sold to biomass producers like biorefinery, biochar unit among others, volume and prices made the project unviable in terms of business. Is more profitable to grow tomatoes, peppers or other not produce products.

4.3 Social impact perspective

A big challenge to afford. Cultural behaviours and prejudices have been the worst barriers to cross.

We designed a gradual approach starting with the bootcamps. The last session was about SGDs focus overall on gender equality.

In general terms, we had first feedback from women to identify social and economic issues linked with gender equality. Côte d'Ivoire is the only one without women participants where we have no inputs about it. For Côte d'Ivoire we made another strategy to afford the gender equality perspective.

After bootcamps we visited one by one all the companies. We had the opportunity to be alone, face to face, and that moment was crucial to build an initial relationship, very important in terms of commitment and trust.

The individual approach was relevant for all the project but even more for the gender perspective.

With all the information after the training program we conclude to focus the gender equality KPIs on the household reality. That means, understand roles and economic independence of women in rural households.

Main objective has been to understand the gender equality situation and try to share some good practices between participants and implement some new activities related with biobased technologies.

We have identified different projects to run during the accelerator program involving women to improve gender equality.

We have studied equality educational programs examples in Uganda and Senegal, and we have identified potential projects to be managed by women. For example, fish pellets production project in Côte d'Ivoire or new business line like briquettes, in Senegal, Uganda and Côte d'Ivoire.

We would like to present the initial gender diagnosis.

We didn't have all the data we need. Not all the questionnaires have been filled and sometimes we did not receive any feedback from the participants. However, we have some interesting conclusions coming from informal chats and incipient data.

To understand and propose some gender equality actions during the Bio4africa project we tried to select and study KPIs aligned with World Bank gender strategy. The strategy aims to accelerate gender equality for all with an emphasis on three aspirational strategic objectives:

- end gender-based violence and elevate human capital
- expand and enable economic opportunities
- engage women as leaders

We defined the principal KPIs to measure and understand better gender equality in African rural areas.

We analyse known data providing from formal information like accountancy, capitalisation table or organization chart and soft data from questionnaires or interviews.

KNOWN DATA

Management roles

- CEO, we have four women in this position.
- Board, we have two examples of women being part of the Board

Salary/incomes

We have data about money only from Senegal.

- Amount. Workers on the field from 35€ to 50€ per month. Workers on the transformation unit from 60€ to 70€. Maximum salary is for responsible on the transformation unit around 138€.
- Frequency. One hundred per cent are seasonal in rural areas that means between 4 and 5 months. Frequency it's longer on transformation unit. Two or three more months.
- Contractual relationship. One hundred per cent are informal with workers on the field, they don't have contract. Only women engaged in administration responsibilities have contract.

SOFT DATA

Property (land)

Property of land in rural Africa is a big issue to resolve, only 10% is registered. Countries want to resolve this situation because they would like to receive taxes but there are a lot of barriers and resistance from different stakeholders. Women own only the 15% of 10% registered land.

Household social situation

- How many children do they have to take care? The average is between 5 and 10.
- Who decides how to spend the money in the household? Only women can decide when they are alone or
- How many hours a day do they have to spend in household works? Minimum three or four. This average is worst when women live without water near the house. Women and girls are in charge of this.

Rural area reality

We have not received data and no one was enough open to talk about these issues.

- How far is the work from the household?
- How far is the school from the household?
- Do they have water on their village?

Conclusions, objectives and actions

Women have access to own small business or being part of agro-cooperatives in few rural areas. Concerning Bio4africa project we have only examples in Senegal and Uganda.

Women as a worker can received a salary only in some kind of crops. Some examples coming from the accelerator program (1) cacao in Côte d'Ivoire there are less than 10% of women working in (2) cashew nuts in Senegal 100% women working in (3) Sunflower in Uganda around 70% women working in (4) mango in Senegal 100% working in.

Economic independence and living conditions like access to water are very important challenges to achieve and limitations to avoid.

Gender equality in rural areas starts at primary school. Girls have so many limitations to go through every day. That's why is very important to ensure enough money in households and provide better conditions to help women to decide to spend their income on education.

Working in this direction we are empowering women at same time.

Equality in short time is 100 x100 linked with economic independence and safety live conditions.

5. RESULTS

We would like to present the best examples done in the accelerator program concerning triple perspective Management, circular economy and social impact.

5.1 Management

Best example done in the accelerator program concerning fit to market.

Mango vinegar in Senegal.

Initial situation. 25.000 litres capacity per year. Initially bottles of 1 litre or 1,5 litres for local market.

We have identified a new client for the company – tourists visiting Senegal.

We have changed the size of the bottle, form 1 or 1,5 Litres to 250ccl. We have redesigned the size thinking in new clients (tourists). Vinegar is very well appreciated by tourist in Senegal, they are open to buy small sizes, easier to transport at better prices. You can find one litre of mango vinegar in the local market at 2.000 Francs CFA. Tourists can pay 3.000 Francs CFA per 250 ccl bottle of mango vinegar. That means potentially multiplying the revenues per 4 transforming the same volume of natural mango to vinegar.

Next challenge is the distribution. How to be present in places where tourists can buy like: small boutiques in the international airport, small markets near petrol stations, boutiques in hotels, small corners in restaurants or tourist local markets among others.

Big issue is to invest in vehicles and human resources.

First action was to test the market in two places with tourists as a pilot and results was great. Next step will be finding financial and human resources to scale the pilot.

Another change we are trying to do to increase the price of 250cl mango vinegar bottle is to switch plastic in glass. There is a local supplier working for other brands but we have not received a proposal in terms of quantities and prices until now.

A glass bottle of mango vinegar 250cl capacity can be paid at 3.500 Francs CFA.

We would like to present different examples concerning productivity.

Sunflower oil in Uganda

10.000 tones oil processed per year. Sales are mainly focus on national and international market in bulk. Prices floating every season around 2 dollars litre. In bulk prices goes down even more.

The strategy is to increase the position in local market selling bottles of one litre and increase capacity to maintain national and international markets.

There is a program to increase the capacity starting from farmers unit plantation.

To facilitate a better production the cooperative bought a tractor. Is a new service “pay per use”. Every farmer has the possibility to use the tractor and paid for it. The cooperative has also small vehicles to move the crop to the transformation unit.

PKWI developed a permanent training program focus on productivity.

Some processes of the transformation unit has been modified to increase the capacity and cover the new estimated volume of production.

Forecast was to increase around 5% the capacity. That means 500 Tones more per year.

Potential revenues for local market are the result to multiply 500.000 bottles more in local market per 2 dollars and maintain national and international markets in bulk.

Local market is ready to buy more but PKWI should define an ambitious strategy to distribute and sell all this quantity.

Dry mango in Senegal

Two transformation units working in the same area in Senegal offering similar products. 70% of the production is sold in bulk at low price for national market and the rest in small packaging better price for local market. They produce also juices and marmalades for local market.

We have defined a strategy of partnership focus on price and volume.

Price will be increased by getting a Bio certification and volume is going to increase through joining both structures and buying more raw material (natural mango) thanks of synergies and better costs and logistics.

Companies are committed in this partnership and they are starting the Bio certification process. In terms of volume, they have improved some transformation processes, they have more capacity to buy and next step could be to include biobased technologies during the transformation process to reduce energy costs.

We would like to present different examples concerning financial perspective.

Cashew nuts in Senegal

Small business with capacity to growth thanks to a client introduced in national and international markets. Big issue is money to buy raw material (natural cashew nuts) and capacity to invest in better machines and processus to dry and pack, market is not a problem.

In Bio4africa project we helped to design and evaluate the possibility to be prepaid by the client to facilitate new purchases. Purchase is a key processus in this kind of business. International buyers come at the same time with big orders during the starting season and prices flows from one week to another and orders are hard to get without cash.

Next season probably this business will be able to increase their purchases in 20% more minimum thanks to receive the money from the client in advance.

5.2 Circular economy

We have been working whit three companies with the objective to implement one bio-based solution before the end of the program. We called the flag companies:

Ethicajou - Fair trade in Senegal – cashew

A unique sector built with producers.

Ethicajou is a social enterprise that brings together at its creation three producers' cooperatives: FECEB, FDPK, N'Galou - an NGO , Agronomes et Vétérinaires Sans Frontières, and Ethiquable.

It was in Kolda in Casamance, a fairly poor region of Senegal, that the NGO AVSF identified the needs feeding the Ethicajou project in 2018. This region, far from central power, is fairly forgotten. The need for job creation there is very strong.

Cashew nuts in Kolda are a symbol of the setbacks of globalization. The region is suitable for growing cashew nuts, but cashew nuts are not shelled in the country. Senegal produces about 35,000 tons of cashew nuts per year and there was only one processing plant.

The nuts are purchased by Vietnamese or Chinese companies which then process them in Asia in conditions that are disastrous for the health of the workers, before sending them to European markets.

In total, a double disadvantage: this type of sector confiscates from farming families the significant added value that they could derive from processing, while the merchandise travels around the world before reaching the end customers, contributing to the increase in greenhouse gases.

Giving producers back their place in the sector, creating added value, driving economic momentum by limiting the carbon impact are the three pillars of the Ethicajou social enterprise.

An unprecedented status in the field of food sectors which brings together three producer cooperatives - FECEB , FDPK , N'Gal - an NGO , Agronomes et Vétérinaires Sans Frontières, and a cooperative company: Ethiquable.

PKWI Cooperative, Uganda

P'kwi was founded in 1993 during the insurgency in teso region that left the rural women exposed to atrocities of war and civil strife. A group of 12 women started the initiative that has now successfully grown beyond a self-help group to a well-established and recognized farm organization with established formal structures. P'kwi uses a unique household model to achieve its vision that brings together five households to constitute a club, five clubs to constitute an economic group, five to ten economic groups to constitute an constitute a sub – cluster and ten sub clusters make up the P'kwi community of 2500 households, a total of 15000 members.

Our Vision

Socially acceptable, environmentally responsible and economically viable rural households in bukedea and teso at large.

Our Mission

To transform the family farm as a model of sustainable organic agriculture by facilitating education, interaction and trade in teso region.

Our Objective

To unlock, rejuvenate, mainstream and interface the indigenous knowledge system and rural information systems.

The Specific objectives:

1. To unlock, rejuvenate, mainstream and interface the indigenous knowledge system and rural information systems with other forms so encouraging the member's spirit of practical thriftiness, mutual self-help and education.
2. To set in motion a farmer-to-farmer sustainable organic agricultural training of members of the cooperative to enable them to acquire new knowledge and skills from other cultures which they deem necessary for their social, economic and cultural transformation.
3. To assist the rural households (family farm as a popular production unit) to identify, develop and put into use local ideas and initiatives into practicable and implementable projects
4. To establish rural information system resource and documentation facility which will make it available to the grass root communities. Such resources are traditional and other forms of music, dance and drama, books, manuals, pamphlets, booklets, films, videos, tapes and other training materials for their use and consultation.
5. To facilitate the setting up of cooperative development revolving fund so as to provide low interest loans to the community group members or clubs and to deal with the objective of improving and adding value to the grass root group products.
6. To collectively process, package and market the members produce thus enable the small holder farmer to enjoy more favourable sales opportunity and increased income for investment and growth.
7. To enhance the active participation in a favourable influence by the local grass root community on local issues and the poverty policies.

8. To enter into any arrangements and agreements with any government, authority, supreme, municipal, public, private, local or otherwise that may seem to be of importance to the cooperative

The Pkwi Cooperatives Office works to develop, grow and support the local farmers as a means of socio-economic development for individuals and local communities, training program to build the capacity of the Pkwi team, cooperative leaders and other training which are as mentioned below

Production, processing and selling of virgin sunflower cooking oil, available in 1, 3, 5, 10, 20 litres.

Production, processing and selling of high-quality cassava flour (HQCF) and chips.

Make and sell primary school uniform for schools around and outside P'kwi.

Production of citrus fruit for the market.

Bake and sell mandaz (cassava and wheat flour), donuts (cassava and wheat flour), bagiya (cassava flour and cowpeas), party cakes (cassava and wheat flour) and chapatti.

Do exchange visits to other farmer organizations.

KAPATCHIVA Cooperative, Ivory Coast

KAPATCHIVA was founded on October 10, 2003, in the Marahoué region, in the Bouaflé department, in the BONON sub-prefecture, with 1,190 members including 58 women. It now has 2,782 members including 272 women. KAPATCHIVA's mission as a member of the ECOOKIM union is to position itself as a reference cooperative in the battle against child labour and the development of modern and professional farmers through the control and appropriation of good agricultural, environmental, and social practices.

KAPATCHIVA's mission is to contribute to:

- Bringing out professional members who produce high-quality cocoa in a sustainable manner.
- Eliminate all forms of child labour through improving the current system.
- Initiate a sustainable socio-economic development dynamic among rural communities in intervention areas

The values of the KAPATCHIVA cooperative can be summarized as follows:

- Strong management organization
- Resource management integrity
- Membership solidarity
- Equity in the delivery of services

Growing and Processing

Cacao production requires an annual rainfall of more than 1,200 mm, as well as a rich and deep soil. It is a perennial plant that begins to produce, for well-managed hybrids, from the second year after planting and has

a lifespan of thirty years. The quality of the planting material chosen is critical to ultimately decide the optimum yields of the members' future plantation. As a result, KAPATCHIVA recommends its growers to use suitable plant material through proper agricultural practices and procedures. It is made up of early hybrids (that go into production in the second year), which are strong, high-producing, and resistant to threats. For one hectare of a plantation, 50 selected mature pods are required; which yields about 1500 plants. These pods are available for members between October and January. We harvest the pods when they are three-quarters yellow, orange, or red after the nursery and cocoa planting stages. The fermenting process allows the precursors of the chocolate aroma to emerge. Members of the cooperative drop the beans in thin layers (3 to 4 centimetres thick) on fixed or mobile elevated clears to accomplish this. They stir constantly and sort the beans to remove any that are faulty or flat. After drying, control and storage entail keeping the cocoa dry to prevent mold, insect growth, and the creation of free fatty acids. This control involves checking the humidity of the cocoa to ensure that it meets marketing standards. Finally, the finished product is sent to the manufacturing plant for maintenance and marketing.

Market situation 2024 and implementation process

Ethicajou cooperative, Senegal

Currently there is a lack of stock of organic cashew nuts this year from Ethicajou's partner cooperatives (approximately 24 tons of nuts acquired out of a total requirement of 300 tons). This is largely due to a drop in production at the plantation level (climate change, heat wave that hit during the cashew flowering period between March and April, furthermore the regulation of an internal marketing market absent and to the detriment of manufacturers). The consequence was a lower supply in the face of a very high demand causing the farm gate purchase prices to explode despite the significant efforts made by the Board of Directors to increase the purchase price of cashew nuts to 600 CFA francs per Kg.

Faced with this situation and after studying the very negative economic impact of putting the company on standby with the option of technical unemployment of part of the staff, by a majority vote, the past board of directors therefore decided to proceed with the dismissal for economic reasons of the entire team.

Today, there is zero stock in store and Ethicajou is sending the remaining almonds from 2023 and the few purchased and processed in 2024 to the main customer in France to honour at least part of the sales contract. The company is closed. The AVSF team is working on a study of a plan to revive activities in 2025 with certainly a new organization of things and even review the economic model. This work will begin in October until the end of November 2024.

Bio-based solutions implemented

Cancelled.

PKWI Cooperative, Uganda

P'KWI is improving:

Women have been able to open a SACCO where they save, loan out money and get interest. Some of them are buying their own plots, run businesses and around 15 are in leadership positions.

For oil, we now have more oil because we now have a machine with a capacity of 2 tonnes a day.

In 2024 we purchased around 35,000 Kg of grain and we processed around 800 L of oil.

We are yet to purchase a machine for making briquets and to find a trainer to train women on how to make soap by next year.

The tractor had a lot of breakdowns and it didn't do much last year. Most farmers fields are not well prepared. Some don't dig out logs from the garden so this causes breakdown of the tractor.

Bio-based solutions implemented

Purchase of a briquetting machine

KAPATCHIVA Cooperative, Ivory Coast

Productions' increased a 10%, and 100% of product was sold.

Bio-based solutions implemented

Tony's Chocolonely Foundation's project:

Project: PRODUCTION AND USE OF BIOCHAR FOR SOIL AMENDMENT

- **What are you trying to achieve?**

We are trying to answer to the expectation of Kapatchiva cooperative to improve soil physicochemical properties by using Biochar as soil amendment biological material.

- **What are you asking for?**

We are asking for financial and material resources to achieve this goal.

- **Core objective and mission of the organisation and project.**

The general objective of this collaboration is to implement the KAPATCHIVA company acceleration program as part of the Bio4Africa project, specifically by:

- Training cooperative members in the construction of the pyrolysis ovens,
- Training cooperative members in Biochar production, and
- Training cooperative members in Biochar application in field through a demonstrative approach.

Table of success indicators:

Relevance:

- **What is the reason for this initiative? What problem does it solve?**

As all west African countries, Côte d'Ivoire is facing climate change which pressure (drought and high temperatures) is mostly observed in agricultural regions such as cocoa production zones of the country like Kapatchiva cooperative cites located in the centre-west. This drought condition compromises cocoa production (the main activity of the cooperative's members) by degrading soil quality and plants health. The potential and fair solution identified by Kapatchiva cooperative thanks to Bio4Africa Project is biochar, a bioresource produced by agricultural waste pyrolysis that can be used to boost soil quality and yields of cocoa plantations.

Indicators	Target
Quantity of biochar	18 tons in 6 months
Number of participants trained	15 pilots cocoa producers
Number of kilns installed in Kapatchiva zone	1
Surface of plantation treated	7 ha during 6 months trials
Level of soils physicochemical properties improved	Amended soils

- **What do you want to do about it? What's your initiative?**

We will produce biochar by using cocoa pods (waste) in pyrolysis technology developed by Bio4Africa project team of INP-HB (in Yamoussoukro, Côte d'Ivoire).

- **Why is your initiative useful and necessary?**

Thanks to its unique chemical and physical attributes and the way it interacts with the soil, biochar has the ability to improve soil health, soil aeration, microorganisms' dynamics and to sequester carbon, and so, it promotes cocoa yields increase and economic opportunities either for biochar producers and farmers. That why their training is important to allow them to produce their own biochar from their cocoa pods to increase their income.

- **What does it add to existing initiatives?**

Biochar improves plant productivity through the gradual release of minerals and trace elements, and thus, contributes to reduce the quantities of chemical fertilizers out of reach of small farmers. It catalyses and amplifies the action of traditional organic or mineral fertilizers when associated. Biochar has also the ability to boost soil water retention to prevent rapid drought, a quality that other traditional fertilizers do not have.

- **How is this initiative particularly relevant to the region? geographic area?**

Kapatchiva Cooperative is a member of a great consortium of cooperatives spread in all cocoa production zones of the country. As said above, all these zones face the same challenge. This initiative is particularly

relevant to all geographic areas of cocoa production because its successful implementation will contribute to sustainable cocoa production in Côte d'Ivoire.

- **Who needs the initiative and how does it manifest itself?**

The target population is all the farmers of the Kapatchiva cooperative which has over 5,000 members; most of them are involved in cocoa production and the others in cash crops production. However, the entire farming community will benefit indirectly from the project's spin-offs. The Kapatchiva cooperative leaders manifest their interest to implement this initiative in their covered zones.

- **Who is involved in making it happen, and with what kind of commitment?**

At the end of various stages of collaboration between Kapatchiva and INP-HB, the pilot partner for the Bio4Africa Project in Côte d'Ivoire, among the various technologies deployed by INP-HB, the company's choice fell on the production and use of biochar to amend cocoa soil. In order to act on this decision, the Cooperative leaders (the Director and a collaborator) held a working session with INP-HB Bio4Africa Project Team, to discuss the technical and financial feasibility of implementing this initiative, in the framework of the acceleration program of the Project.

- **Did you involve the target group in project planning?**

Surveys were carried out to understand the realities of the target population. As a result, the target population encouraged their cooperative leaders to get involved in the implementation of the project, considering its vital impact on the sustainable fertility of their soil.

Project objective and activities:

- **What is the overall objective (plus thematic - impact and results)?**

The overall objective is to implement the Kapatchiva company acceleration program as part of the Bio4Africa project, and contribute to sustainably improving the productivity of cocoa through the use of Biochar for soil amendment.

- **What are the activities (concrete results)?**

At the end of the training courses by INP-HB project Team, participants will be able to :

- Built pyrolysis kilns for biochar production for themselves
- Use the kilns to produce ready-to-use biochar from cocoa pods biomass by pyrolysis technology deployed by INP-HB
- Use the biochar produced to amend agricultural soil and sell biochar to other farmers
- Increase their yield and income, leading to reducing poverty occurring in cocoa production zones and facilitating their children's scholarship.

Project duration:

- **When will the project take place?**

The project will take place during the year 2024 as soon as it is accepted, as the rainy season starts.

- **Can it be divided into phases?**

This project will be divided into four (4) phases:

- **What will be the key moments and milestones?**

- (1) training Kapatchiva members in construction of pyrolysis kilns for biochar production (on receipt of funding, and during 15-20 days)
- (2) Training Kapatchiva members in biochar production from raw material (cocoa pods) (during 3-5 days after kiln construction),
- (3) training in the use of Biochar through agronomic trials in real environment on INP-HB experimental cite (during one day), and (4) carrying out field trials on Kapatchiva pilots' members plots of land (if this phase is funded).

- **When will the project be completed?**

The project will be completed approximatively one month after receipt of funding for the training phases and six months for field trials in Kapatchiva zones.

- **Is there a clear end point?**

The duration of the training courses will depend on the activities concerned (2 days for materials purchasing or providing, 15-20 days for building the oven according to the existing model, 3-5 days for biochar production and 1 day for training cooperative participants members for agronomic field use). The implementation of the fourth phase depends on the funding and may take 6 months to be completed.

So, the clear end point is seven months after the beginning.

Expected results and impact :

- **Who will be affected by the initiative, and how important is it to the target group?**

The target population is all the farmers of the Kapatchiva cooperative, which has over 5,000 members, some of whom are involved in cocoa production and others in cash crop production. However, the entire Bonon farming community will benefit indirectly from the project's spin-offs.

The initiative is important insofar as producers are able to produce biochar and use it to improve their soil in a sustainable way.

- **What do you want to achieve in terms of measurable results?**

- The ability of participants to build pyrolysis ovens for biochar production,
- The ability of participants to produce biochar for their own use,
- The ability of participants to apply the biochar produced to improve agricultural soil

- **How do you know when you've reached your goal? What will you measure?**

When after the training, we will observe that the participants and other cooperative members have installed pyrolysis kilns, produced routinely biochar and used it for their cocoa soil amendment and when this improves their yields and income.

- **When is the project a success?**

The project is a success if measurable results can be seen in the field, at namely the pyrolysis furnaces for Biochar production built by the producers, crops yield and income continuously increase, and soil fertility improved.

Our partners:

- **Who is involved in this project? And why?**

The Bio4Africa Project team of the Félix HOUPHOUËT-BOIGNY National Polytechnic Institute (INP-HB) in Yamoussoukro, Côte d'Ivoire, is the partner involved in this project, because the technology to be used is deployed by this Institute, as a pilote partner of Bio4Africa project.

- **Are volunteers involved?**

Many of Kapatchiva members wish to participate to the training, but only a limited number will be involved. Pilote farmers among Kapatchiva members who accepted the field demonstration trials planned will also be involved.

- **Do you need local support/advice (e.g. from cooperatives) of cocoa)?**

We need no further support or advice for this project, out of what INP-HB will provide us.

Project sustainability :

- **How does this project make a lasting difference?**

As a biological soil conditioner, biochar will restore cocoa soil fertility and health without any side effects. This bioresource can be produced by farmers on their own plot of land when and as they need, with a biomass (cocoa pods) always available in their field. So, this project can make a lasting difference because it is set in the circular economy logical.

- **Does it have the potential to launch something bigger?**

This project will be the first one at a cooperative scale, and we trust its success will bring the other cocoa cooperatives throughout the country to follow the Kapatchiva example.

- **How will the impact continue after the project ends?**

As the farmers will be trained to build pyrolysis furnaces, produce biochar and apply it for soil amendment by themselves, the impact of the project will continue even after Tony's and INP-HB have left Kapatchiva. Because the members can produce and use biochar without spending money, on the contrary, they will increase their income by biochar selling, if necessary, to other farmers and by increasing of their cocoa yields.

Governance structure

Overview Include all dynamics, relevant shareholding and voting/economic rights:

The KAPATCHIVA cooperative society is governed by the Uniform Act of 15 December 2010 on the law governing cooperative societies. It is managed by a Board of Directors. Its purposes, directly or indirectly, are:

- to organise and carry out activities relating to the production, collection and sale of coffee, cocoa, cashew nuts, food crops and any other agricultural products produced by its members and likely to contribute to the achievement of its objectives.
- to seek the financing and technical assistance necessary for the sound economic and social development of its members.
- to provide, in whole or in part, all common services necessary for the exercise of the members' production profession.
- acquiring and managing collective equipment for all members.

The bodies of the KAPATCHIVA co-operative with a Board of Directors are: the General Meeting of Co-operative Members, the Board of Directors and the Supervisory Board. All these boards are voted for five years, renewable once.

The INP-HB is a public administrative and technological institution whose mission is to train young and senior (for engineer and doctoral studies) and continuing studies for seniors in the fields of industry, civil engineering, mining, agronomy, management and trade. Scientific and technological research are carried out to support the socio-professional world via Technology transfer.

The governance of INP-HB includes:

- a Management Board
- an Academic Council
- a Scientific council
- a Disciplinary council.

All the members are voted for 5 years by their peer.

5.3 Social impact

The main gender indicator, in the short term, is economic independence

Composition of household incomes for agricultural smallholders

The rural space where agriculture takes place encompasses a wide range of areas from dispersed rural settlements to functionally linked towns where non-farm services and commercial activities occur, generating dynamic economies. Agricultural smallholder households, depending on the context in which they live, can have a myriad of farm and non-farm income sources to feed their incomes.

Based on the literature on rural household incomes (Reardon et al, 2007; Haggblade et al, 2010), we identify three main sources of income: farm net income, non-farm net income, and other income, which essentially represents non-labour income. The summation of the three income sources comprises the smallholder total actual income.

Farm income comes from various sources, as many smallholder farmers in developing economies grow multiple crop species on their farms (Bellon et al, 2020) and raise major and minor livestock units that can be sold and/or supply a wide array of products and by-products (e.g. milk, cheese, eggs, meat, wool, honey,

amongst others)⁵. Such production not only significantly contributes to total household incomes, but is considered an important source of household consumption.

Net non-farm labour income is defined as all income coming from all economic activities other than the production of primary agricultural commodities (farm income).

In rural areas, non-farm earnings account for 35% to 50% of total household incomes (see for example: Reardon et al, 2007; Deininger & Olinto, 2001; Deininger & Okidi, 2001). Non-farm income activities come from a set of wage-employment and self-employment activities. Wage-employment activities involve at least an implicit employment contract or arrangement, where the employer can give orders to the employee (Reardon, 1997). Typical wage-employment activities include hired agricultural labour or working as a teacher in a village. On the other hand, self-employment activities involve ownership of the firm (business or shop) that produces goods or services (Reardon, 1997). Typical self-employment activities are petty trading, cottage industries, handy-crafts, amongst others.

Finally, other non-farm non-labour income relates to other incomes obtained from off-farm non-labour activities, such as cash or in-kind gifts, public or private transfers, remittances, amongst others.

In our cohort of 20 companies, we have 4 examples of economic independence:

- Agropastoral SCPL, Senegal
- Waare SCPL, Senegal
- Demiiir SCPL, Senegal
- PKWI cooperative, Uganda

6. MAIN FACTORS TO FAIL

Why are the results for December 2024 the same as the initial results from December 2023?

Factors that have limited the implementation of improvements:

1. **Financial issues:**
 - a. Lack of cash flow
 - b. Difficult access to financing

2. **Value proposition:** Price/unit is the start point. We have identified three examples:
 - a. Local market selling not processed products without add value. Commodities like tomatoes, lettuce, rice, etc. that means low prices.
 - b. National market selling processed products like mango dry, mango vinegar or sunflower oil, that means better price
 - c. International market selling processed products like bio cashew nuts that means much better price.

3. **Lack of willingness to invest in the business:** Some small farmers are not the owners of the land. We have not a reliable data from our participants in the accelerator program but is a significant issue. This first premise determines investments, could explain a lack of long-term management, and creates a potentially risky situation.
4. **Variability in annual production:**
 - a. Climatic problems
 - b. Access to purchased seeds
 - c. Decreased soil fertility
5. **Short-term business culture:**
 - a. No planning
 - b. No financing is sought for business growth
6. **Informality in agreements:**
 - a. Changes in prices
 - b. Failure to deliver the ordered products

7. THE FOUR BUSINESS MODELS

7.1 Small farmer alone selling not processed products

This is a very basic model in terms of management. In fact, when the unit farm is around 1Ha, its more appropriate to define this model in terms of subsistence not business.

Normally is a family without employees harvesting, selling and managing all the farm at the same time, with credit and treasury difficulties.

In general, small farmers harvest different crops at the same time. In Ghana, for example, we have small farmers producing okra, tomatoes, lettuce, pepper in one farm.

All of these products are commodities, not singular or different from the concurrence, that means local market and low price.

We have also to take in account productivity. Not all the potential capacity is harvested, the percentage lost is minus income. We have also to realize, in this kind of farms, part of the production goes to the family, this also reduces the potential income. The rest goes to the market.

It's not difficult to understand sales are going to be reduced. That's why every small cost has a relevant impact in terms of margin.

We have determined two kinds of basic costs, variables and fixed. Principal variable costs are: fertilizers, pesticides, insecticides, fungicides, credit, seeds, purchases, transport. Basic fixed costs are: costs of land, small machines and agricultural tools.

Result is a no profit. Not enough to have money to run the business without credit. We identified a high level of risk. Every negative impact coming from the costs, productivity or devaluation of prices could strangle the business.

How biobased technologies can improve this model. Potential improvements related with Bio4africa biobased technologies project could Increase productivity and reduce cost of fertilizers.

In this model social impact, overall focus on gender, has a very difficult approach and treatment. There are big barriers to overcome like roles between men and women, not paid work, background education and cultural behaviours. Reliable data and transparency to understand the real situation are also large deficits.

The analysis of this this model concludes, household incomes providing from the farm activity could represent the 50% to 65%, no farm labour incomes, coming from goods or services is the rest to achieve the 100%. Petty trading, cottage industries or handy crafts are typical activities.

Another livelihood is no farm no labour incomes obtained form off farm non labour activities such as cash or in-kind gifts, public or private transfers amongst others.

Figure 1. Small farmer alone selling not processed products.

CONCLUSIONS

Risky position. Every negative impact can struggle the business, insecurity.

No profit. High costs and low prices, not singular value proposition - commodities products.

No capacity to growth. The lack of credit and treasury without benefits from the activity.

No possibility to include biobased technologies. No capacity to invest not enough volume.

Social impact on gender equality. Strong cultural barrier. No capacity to transform the household roles one by one.

7.2 Small farmer being part of a cooperative selling not processed products

In general terms medium and big cooperatives has thousands of families onboard. Every family manage a farm. In average, farms are 2Ha size. In single product farms like mango, cacao or rice that number increases. The average is 2,5Ha.

In small farms is a family without employees harvesting, selling and managing all the farm at the same time, with credit and treasury difficulties. In bigger farms there are employees.

All of these products are commodities, not singular or different from the concurrence, that means local market and low price.

We have also to take in account productivity. Not all the potential capacity is harvested, the percentage lost is minus income. We have also to realize, in this kind of farms, part of the production goes to the family, this also reduces the potential income. The rest goes to the market.

Cooperatives facilitates a better costs prices and access to market and credits. Cooperatives can give better prices in: fertilizers, pesticides, insecticides, fungicides, credit, seeds, purchases, transport. Sometimes cooperatives can also provide small machines and agricultural tools.

Result is a reduced profit. Sometimes not enough to run the business without credit.

How biobased technologies can improve this model. Potential improvements related with Bio4africa biobased technologies project could Increase productivity and reduce cost of fertilizers.

In this model social impact, overall focus on gender, could come only from the cooperative. The approach and treatment are not easier but we studied cooperatives with very interesting gender programs inside. There are big barriers to overcome like roles between men and women, not paid work, background education and cultural behaviours. Reliable data and transparency to understand the real situation are also large deficits.

The analysis of this this model concludes, household incomes providing from the farm activity could represent the 60% to 70%, no farm labour incomes, coming from goods or services is the rest to achieve the 100%. Petty trading, cottage industries or handy crafts are typical activities.

Another livelihood is no farm no labour incomes obtained form off farm non labour activities such as cash or in-kind gifts, public or private transfers amongst others.

Figure 2. Small farmer being part of a cooperative selling not processed products.

CONCLUSIONS

Low risky position. Be part of a big group, security.

Reduced profit. Better costs and low prices.

Difficult to growth. Not substantial benefits from the activity difficult investment and improvements.

Possibility to include biobased technologies. They have volume but spread around the territory. The big challenge is to collect and move all the feedstock from each plantation. Logistics and investment in vehicles and biobased technology. This kind of cooperatives has problems to invest.

Social impact on gender equality. Strong cultural barrier, capacity to transform household roles through programs coming from the cooperative. The cooperative is the key but few (small and medium cooperatives with not processed products) have this objective on mind.

7.3 Small farmer being part of a cooperative selling certified products

In general terms medium and big cooperatives have thousands of families onboard. Every family manage a farm. On average, farms are 2Ha size. In single product farms like mango, cacao or rice that number increases. The average is 2,5Ha.

In small farms is a family without employees harvesting, selling and managing all the farm at the same time, with credit and treasury difficulties. In bigger farms there are employees.

Certified products are singular they have a different position from the concurrence, that means international market and high price.

In general terms certified products come from one single plantation. In the accelerator program we have cashew nuts and cacao. Cooperatives are manly focus to help on productivity. This is a key indicator because certified products make sense with large quantities.

Cooperatives facilitate training and resources to increase productivity and also general services to achieve better costs prices, access to market and credits.

The result is a profit. Depending of market prices, farmers have the capacity to invest.

How biobased technologies can improve this model. Potential improvements related with Bio4africa biobased technologies project could Increase productivity, reduce cost of fertilizers and access to products like briquettes, nutrients for animals among others.

In this model social impact, overall focus on gender, could come only from the cooperative. The approach and treatment are not easier but we studied cooperatives with very interesting gender programs inside. There are big barriers to overcome like roles between men and women, not paid work, background education and cultural behaviours. Reliable data and transparency to understand the real situation are also large deficits.

The analysis of this this model concludes, household incomes providing from farm activity could represent the 80% to 90%, and no farm labour incomes, coming from goods or services is the rest to achieve the 100%. Petty trading, cottage industries or handy crafts are typical activities.

Another livelihood is no farm no labour incomes obtained form off farm non labour activities such as cash or in-kind gifts, public or private transfers amongst others.

Figure 3. Small farmer being part of a cooperative selling certified products.

CONCLUSIONS

Low risky position. Be part of a big group, security.

Better profit. Better costs and high prices. Certified products could be 200% better prices.

Capacity to growth. Profits from the activity afford investment and improvements.

Possibility to include biobased technologies. They have volume but spread around the territory. The big challenge is to collect and move all the feedstock from each plantation. Logistics and investment in vehicles and biobased technology. This kind of cooperatives has the possibility to invest. They have also access to loans or soft debt through partners-international clients.

Social impact on gender equality. Strong cultural barrier, capacity to transform household roles through programs coming from the cooperative. This kind of cooperatives are oriented to improve gender equality, is part of their strategy.

7.4 Small farmer being part of a cooperative selling processed products

In general terms medium and big cooperatives has thousands of families onboard. Every family manage a farm. In average, farms are 2Ha size. In single product farms like mango, cacao or rice that number increases. The average is 2,5Ha.

In small farms is a family without employees harvesting, selling and managing all the farm at the same time, with credit and treasury difficulties. In bigger farms there are employees.

Processed products have add value, is a final product. Production capacity, certification, packaging and marketing position are key factors to jump from national to international market. We have both examples in the accelerator program. Obviously international market is better price but a good strategy in national market can be extremely profitable.

In general terms processed products come from one single planation. In the accelerator program we have mango, cashew nuts and sunflower. Cooperatives are manly focus to help on productivity. This is a key indicator because processed products in general terms have sense with large quantities.

Cooperatives facilitates training and resources to increase productivity and also general services to achieve better costs prices, access to market and credits.

Result is a better profit. Depending of market prices, farmers have capacity to invest.

How biobased technologies can improve this model. Potential improvements related with Bio4africa biobased technologies project could Increase productivity, reduce cost of fertilizers and access to products like briquettes, nutrients for animals among others.

In this model social impact, overall focus on gender, could come only from the cooperative. The approach and treatment are not easier but we studied cooperatives with very interesting gender programs inside. There are big barriers to overcome like roles between men and women, not paid work, background education and cultural behaviours. Reliable data and transparency to understand the real situation are also large deficits.

The analysis of this this model concludes, household incomes providing from the farm activity could represent the 80% to 90%, no farm labour incomes, coming from goods or services is the rest to achieve the 100%. Petty trading, cottage industries or handy crafts are typical activities.

Another livelihood is no farm no labour incomes obtained form off farm non labour activities such as cash or in-kind gifts, public or private transfers amongst others.

Figure 4. Small farmer being part of a cooperative selling processed products.

CONCLUSIONS

Low risky position. Be part of a big group, security.

Better profit. Better costs and better prices. Processed products have better prices.

Capacity to growth. Profits from the activity afford investment and improvements.

Possibility to include biobased technologies. The transformation process generates a lot of waste that can be used in biobased technologies producing new products and/or producing energy.

Social impact on gender equality. Strong cultural barrier, capacity to transform household roles through programs coming from the cooperative. Most of this kind of cooperatives are oriented to improve gender equality, is part of their strategy.

8. SCALABLE METHODOLOGY

The design of the business growth programme of BIO4AFRICA has been shaped by the long experience of Barcelona Business Platform (BPE) in such programmes, both in Europe and South America, together with the methods in business acceleration shared through the international network Fledge (The conscious company accelerator <https://www.fledge.co/locations/>), of which BPE is a partner and responsible for the implementation of the programme in Barcelona <http://fledge-barcelona.org/en/>.

The programme design is the result of applying our method considering the realities of the different cohorts selected in each country and the characteristics of the BIO4AFRICA project.

With respect to our method, we have made the following adjustments:

- Selection process

Without using the FS6 platform <https://www.f6s.com/>, and with the support of local partners to filter candidates. We decide not to use FS6 as we done usually because the complexity of the process (four countries with three focus farmers, transformation and recycling companies). On the other hand, we would like to reenforce the collaboration of the local partners taking advantage of their contacts and knowledge of the environment.

- Training

We have replaced an 8-week programme in Barcelona with four programmes, one in each country, in a very intense one-week boot camp. We have trained local trainers to execute de the program with the same quality. In order to achieve the same results, we have designed a field visit by the BPE consultant to each and every one of the participants to review and agree concepts and learnings about business strategy and control.

The rest of the programme follows the standard method, where monitoring and business support are the key to success, as participants are accompanied to implement the advice and learnings from the training.

It is also in this phase of the programme that access is facilitated to the financing required to grow and consolidate the companies.

The key processes that determine the design of the programme are:

1. Selection of candidates
2. Training (Bootcamps, one to one visits and mentoring program)
3. Monitoring and business support

- Together with the participants, define the road map to be executed during the period January to December 24
- Roadmap execution
- Fluid relationship via email or WhatsApp regarding business decisions and the search for financing
- Gathering six-monthly economic management and positive impact KPIs
- Monitoring circular economy implementation

Adjustments that would allow the program to scale:

- Training with local teams
- Change the 8-weeks training to an intense bootcamp
- Review the training content
- Adjust the training to the needs of the participating businesses
- Train local consultants to provide closer on-site follow-up to the implementation of improvements

9. CONCLUSIONS

1. We have successfully done the training program.

It was a great challenge to develop the training program in four countries with local trainers in some countries, participants coming with different management backgrounds and known economic and social environments.

Finally, we can conclude we achieved the objective. We have trained with the triple approach – bootcamps, mentors and visits, twenty business along the agrobusiness value chain.

We have been working and understanding much better the economic situation in every step of the value chain thanks to the different business selected.

During all the training program we gathered the relevant information. Formal information through standard tools like Business model, P&L, Balance etc. and informal information through interviews. We must notify we missed more data from the participants related with economic figures and over all about gender perspective.

The result was a business diagnosis under the methodology of triple perspective – management, circular economy and social impact - per each one.

2. We have identified the four business models to understand which model suites best to include bio-based solutions

Next step was to defined a standard unit to compare the different positions in the value chain. The standard unit we have decided to compare is the farm.

We have studied the social and economic reality about the management of one small farm from four different positions:

1. Small farmer alone selling not processed products
2. Small farmer part of a cooperative selling not processed products
3. Small farmer part of a cooperative selling certified products
4. Small farmer part of a cooperative selling processed products

The objective is to understand which model suites best to include biobased technologies and measure the benefit of the triple perspective: management. Circular economy and social impact.

We start the study from the following premises:

- Property is a key indicator

Some small farmers are not the owners of the land. We have not a reliable data from our participants in the accelerator program but is a significant issue. This first premise determines investments, could explain a lack of long-term management, and creates a potentially risky situation.

- Size sets income level

Small farm unit extension is from 1Ha to 3ha of land.

- Organization model facilitates better margins
 To be part of a cooperative improves margins. Cooperatives could help in access to market and could provide services related with the expenses like seeds, transport, fertilizers or credits. Another relevant aspect to be part of a cooperative is the security.
- Transformation unit
 Installation where products can be processed adding value. We have one examples in the accelerator program like dry cashew nuts and sunflower oil.
- Market is the king
 Price/unit is the start point. We have identified three examples: (1) local market selling not processed products without add value. Commodities like tomatoes, lettuce, rice, etc. that means low prices. (2) national market selling processed products like mango dry, mango vinegar or sunflower oil, that means better price (3) international market selling processed products like bio cashew nuts that means much better price.
- Certifications to add value
 Concerning market and selling price we have to take in account the certifications. There are very relevant for the P&L analysis. Certification Bio and fair-Trade market label are two ways to increase the price. In the accelerator program, all the cooperatives that are selling their products in the international markets has minimum one of them.
- Biobased technologies and circular economy
 We have two different examples. (1) technologies are part of the business model because reduces costs or increases incomes or services. (2) business model can't include biobased technologies because has no viability.
- Social impact
 We have studied the composition household incomes and the role of women in a rural family as a key indicator. Our approach is double (1) measure the income gap into a household economy to achieve a decent standard of living. In rural areas in Africa all the families have other incomes out of the farm activity but not always are enough to ensure a decent quality of living (2) women capacity to decide the destiny of the money like food, education, clothes etc. Capacity in terms of decision, who really manages the familiar economy. Our study is inspired by the living-income theory exposed by GIZ – German international cooperation for a sustainable development, COSA – Committee on sustainability assessment and Kit - Royal Tropical Institute in Guidance on calculating household income version1. (May 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Small farmer selling not processed products

Risky position. Every negative impact can struggle the business, insecurity.

No profit. High costs and low prices, not singular value proposition - commodities products.

No capacity to growth. The lack of credit and treasury without benefits from the activity.

No possibility to include biobased technologies. No capacity to invest not enough volume.

Social impact on gender equality. Strong cultural barrier. No capacity to transform the household roles one by one.

2. Small farmer being part of a cooperative selling not processed products

Low risky position. Be part of a big group, security.

Reduced profit. Better costs and low prices.

Difficult to growth. Not substantial benefits from the activity difficult investment and improvements.

Possibility to include biobased technologies. They have volume but spread around the territory. The big challenge is to collect and move all the feedstock from each plantation. Logistics and investment in vehicles and biobased technology. This kind of cooperatives has problems to invest.

Social impact on gender equality. Strong cultural barrier, capacity to transform household roles through programs coming from the cooperative. The cooperative is the key but few (small and medium cooperatives with not processed products) have this objective on mind.

3. Small farmer being part of a cooperative selling certified products

Low risky position. Be part of a big group, security.

Better profit. Better costs and high prices. Certified products could be 200% better prices.

Capacity to growth. Profits from the activity afford investment and improvements.

Possibility to include biobased technologies. They have volume but spread around the territory. The big challenge is to collect and move all the feedstock from each plantation. Logistics and investment in vehicles and biobased technology. This kind of cooperatives has the possibility to invest. They have also access to loans or soft debt through partners-international clients.

Social impact on gender equality. Strong cultural barrier, capacity to transform household roles through programs coming from the cooperative. This kind of cooperatives are oriented to improve gender equality, is part of their strategy.

4. Small farmer being part of a cooperative selling processed products

Low risky position. Be part of a big group, security.

Better profit. Better costs and better prices. Processed products have better prices.

Capacity to growth. Profits from the activity afford investment and improvements.

Possibility to include biobased technologies. The transformation process generates a lot of waste that can be used in biobased technologies producing new products and/or producing energy.

Social impact on gender equality. Strong cultural barrier, capacity to transform household roles through programs coming from the cooperative. Most of this kind of cooperatives are oriented to improve gender equality, is part of their strategy.

3. We have successfully done the management support program

After the training program we designed roadmap per each participant.

What's a road map? A list of actions – activity, cost and timing - to achieve a strategy starting from an initial business diagnosis. In Bio4Africa accelerator program we have evaluate three perspectives – management, circular economy and social impact.

Management results

Best example done in the accelerator program concerning fit to market.

Mango vinegar in Senegal

Initial situation. 25.000 litres capacity per year. Initially bottles of 1 litre or 1,5 litres for local market.

We have identified a new client for the company: The tourists visiting Senegal.

We have changed the size of the bottle, form 1 or 1,5 Litres to 250ccl. We have redesigned the size thinking in new clients (tourists). Vinegar is very well appreciated by tourist in Senegal, they are open to buy small sizes, easier to transport at better prices. You can find one litre of mango vinegar in the local market at 2.000 Francs CFA. Tourists can pay 3.000 Francs CFA per 250 ccl bottle of mango vinegar. That means potentially to multiply the revenues per 4 transforming the same volume of natural mango to vinegar.

Next challenge is the distribution. How to be present in places where tourists can buy like: small boutiques in the international airport, small markets near petrol stations, boutiques in hotels, small corners in restaurants or tourist local markets among others.

Big issue is to invest in vehicles and human resources.

First action was to test the market in two places with tourists as a pilot and results was great. Next step will be finding financial and human resources to scale the pilot.

Another change we are trying to do to increase the price of 250cl mango vinegar bottle is to switch plastic in glass. There is a local supplier working for other brands but we have not received a proposal in terms of quantities and prices until now.

A glass bottle of mango vinegar 250cl capacity can be paid at 3.500 Francs CFA.

We would like to present different examples concerning productivity.

Sunflower oil in Uganda

10.000 tones oil processed per year. Sales are mainly focus on national and international market in bulk. Prices floating every season around 2 dollars litre. In bulk prices goes down even more.

The strategy is to increase the position in local market selling bottles of one litre and increase capacity to maintain national and international markets.

There is a program to increase the capacity starting from farmers unit plantation.

To facilitate a better production the cooperative bought a tractor. Is a new service “pay per use”. Every farmer has the possibility to use the tractor and paid for it. The cooperative has also small vehicles to move the crop to the transformation unit.

PKWI developed a permanent training program focus on productivity.

Some processes of the transformation unit has been modified to increase the capacity and cover the new estimated volume of production.

Forecast was to increase around 5% the capacity. That means 500 Tones more per year.

Potential revenues for local market are the result to multiply 500.000 bottles more in local market per 2 dollars and maintain national and international markets in bulk.

Local market is ready to buy more but PKWI should define an ambitious strategy to distribute and sell all this quantity.

Dry mango in Senegal

Two transformation units working in the same area in Senegal offering similar products. 70% of the production is sold in bulk at low price for national market and the rest in small packaging better price for local market. They produce also juices and marmalades for local market.

We have defined a strategy of partnership focus on price and volume.

Price will be increased by getting a Bio certification and volume is going to increase through joining both structures and buying more raw material (natural mango) thanks of synergies and better costs and logistics.

Companies are committed in this partnership and they are starting the Bio certification process. In terms of volume, they have improved some transformation processes, they have more capacity to buy and next step could be to include biobased technologies during the transformation process to reduce energy costs.

We would like to present different examples concerning financial perspective.

Cashew nuts in Senegal

Small business with capacity to growth thanks to a client introduced in national and international markets. Big issue is money to buy raw material (natural cashew nuts) and capacity to invest in better machines and processus to dry and pack, market is not a problem.

In Bio4africa project we helped to design and evaluate the possibility to be prepaid by the client to facilitate new purchases. Purchase is a key processus in this kind of business. International buyers come at the same time with big orders during the starting season and prices flows from one week to another and orders are hard to get without cash.

Next season probably this business will be able to increase their purchases in 20% more minimum thanks to receive the money from the client in advance.

Circular Economy Results

PKWI Cooperative, Uganda

Biobased solution implemented: **Briquetting machine**

Kapatchiva Cooperative, Ivory Coast

Biobased solution implemented: **Pyrolysis kilns**

- Build pyrolysis kilns for biochar production for themselves
- Use the kilns to produce ready-to-use biochar from cocoa pods biomass by pyrolysis technology deployed by INP-HB
- Use the biochar produced to amend agricultural soil and sell biochar to other farmers
- Increase their yield and income, leading to reducing poverty occurring in cocoa production zones and facilitating their children scholarship.

Social Impact Results

The main gender indicator, in the short term, is economic independence

Composition of household incomes for agricultural smallholders

The rural space where agriculture takes place encompasses a wide range of areas from dispersed rural settlements to functionally linked towns where non-farm services and commercial activities occur, generating dynamic economies. Agricultural smallholder households, depending on the context in which they live, can have a myriad of farm and non-farm income sources to feed their incomes.

Based on the literature on rural household incomes (Reardon et al, 2007; Haggblade et al, 2010), we identify three main sources of income: farm net income, non-farm net income, and other income, which essentially

represents non-labour income. The summation of the three income sources comprises the smallholder total actual income.

Farm income comes from various sources, as many smallholder farmers in developing economies grow multiple crop species on their farms (Bellon et al, 2020) and raise major and minor livestock units that can be sold and/or supply a wide array of products and by-products (e.g. milk, cheese, eggs, meat, wool, honey, amongst others)⁵. Such production not only significantly contributes to total household incomes, but is considered an important source of household consumption.

Net non-farm labour income is defined as all income coming from all economic activities other than the production of primary agricultural commodities (farm income).

In rural areas, non-farm earnings account for 35% to 50% of total household incomes (see for example: Reardon et al, 2007; Deininger & Olinto, 2001; Deininger & Okidi, 2001). Non-farm income activities come from a set of wage-employment and self-employment activities. Wage-employment activities involve at least an implicit employment contract or arrangement, where the employer can give orders to the employee (Reardon, 1997). Typical wage-employment activities include hired agricultural labour or working as a teacher in a village. On the other hand, self-employment activities involve ownership of the firm (business or shop) that produces goods or services (Reardon, 1997). Typical self-employment activities are petty trading, cottage industries, handy-crafts, amongst others.

Finally, other non-farm non-labour income relates to other incomes obtained from off-farm non-labour activities, such as cash or in-kind gifts, public or private transfers, remittances, amongst others.

In our cohort of 20 companies, we have 4 examples of economic independence:

- Agropastoral SCPL, Senegal
- Waare SCPL, Senegal
- Demiiir SCPL, Senegal
- PKWI cooperative, Uganda

Main Factors To Fail

Why December'2024 results are the same as initial results from December'2023?

Factors that have limited the implementation of improvements:

7. Financial issues:

- a. Lack of cash flow
- b. Difficult access to financing

8. Value proposition: Price/unit is the start point. We have identified three examples:

- a. Local market selling not processed products without add value. Commodities like tomatoes, lettuce, rice, etc. that means low prices.
- b. National market selling processed products like mango dry, mango vinegar or sunflower oil, that means better price
- c. International market selling processed products like bio cashew nuts that means much better price.

9. **Lack of willingness to invest in the business:** Some small farmers are not the owners of the land. We have not a reliable data from our participants in the accelerator program but is a significant issue. This first premise determines investments, could explain a lack of long-term management, and creates a potentially risky situation.

10. Variability in annual production:

- a. Climatic problems
- b. Access to purchased seeds
- c. Decreased soil fertility

11. Short-term business culture:

- a. No planning
- b. No financing is sought for business growth

12. Informality in agreements:

- a. Changes in prices
- b. Failure to deliver the ordered products